

ISic4342

I.Sicily inscription 4342

Language

Latin

Type

funerary

Material

limestone

Object

funerary altar

Editor

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Jonathan Prag

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Autopsy

2011.04.20

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Syracusae

Place of origin (modern)

Siracusa

Provenance

Florida, contrada Monasteri, prop. of Barone Andrea Catalano

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Siracusa, Museo Archeologico
Regionale Paolo Orsi

Physical Description**Dimensions**

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout**Execution**

Engraved

Letter Forms**Letter heights:**

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text**Apparatus****Translation****Commentary****Digital identifiers:****Bibliography**

undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined 1876-.
Notizie degli scavi di antichità. *Notizie degli scavi di antichità*. At 165 no.2 fig.3

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